

Potential Local Anaesthetics. Part III. Synthesis of Basic *N*-(α -Alkyl/aryl/benzyl) Acyl Amides

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To investigate the effect of changes in structure on the local anaesthetic activity of basic *N*-benzyl acyl amides, several similarly constituted compounds have been synthesised.

In continuation of our previous work¹ more compounds have been prepared to collect data on the effect of change in structure on local anaesthetic activity of basic *N*-benzyl acyl amides. In this communication compounds containing alkyl/aryl groups on the α -carbon atom of benzyl group, viz., diethylamino/morpholinyl/piperidinyl-*N*-(α -alkyl/aryl benzyl) acetamides and α' -diethylamino/morpholinyl/piperidinyl-*N*-(α -alkyl/aryl benzyl) propionamides, are described. It is significant to note that some α -phenethyl amines, to which compounds reported in this communication are related, show analgesic activity².

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Alkyl/aryl benzyl amines were prepared by the Leuckart reaction³ from the corresponding ketones. Condensation of α -alkyl/aryl benzyl amines with α -halo-acyl halides and replacement of the halogen by a secondary amine group were carried out as described earlier³. Compounds prepared are recorded in Tables I to IV.

TABLE I

N-(α -Alkyl/aryl benzyl) chloroacetamides.

No.	R.	R ₁ .	M.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Me	Me	105°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ONCl	16.4	16.6
2	4-Cl	"	104°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ONCl ₂	30.7	30.6
3	4-Br	"	90°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ONBrCl	4.9(N)	5.1(N)
4	4-OMe	"	110°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ON ₂ Cl	16.6	15.4
5	3,4-DiCl	"	74°-75°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ONCl ₃	39.8	40.0
6	2,5-DiCl	"	96°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ONCl ₃	39.9	40.0
7	"	Et	110°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ONCl ₃	39.2	38.0
8	H	Ph	122°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ONCl	13.3	13.6

1. Dalal and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 437; 1962, **39**, 191.

2. McCoubrey, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1953, **8**, 22.

3. Ingersoll *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1808; Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2249.

TABLE II

Hydrochloride of α' -*sec.* amino-N-(α' -subst. benzyl) alkylaryl acetamides.

S.No.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.	
I. A = NEt ₂ .									
1	191°	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	9.6	9.8	162°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	9.2	9.4	
2	202°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	9.3	9.2	198°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.6	8.8	
3	170°	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Br ₂ HCl	7.9	8.0	184°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ HCl	7.8	7.7	
4	196°	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	9.5	9.3	173°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	8.7	8.9	
5	165°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.4	8.2	178°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	7.6	7.9	
6	187°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.3	8.2	200°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.0	7.9	
7	194°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.0	7.9	198°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	7.5	7.6	
8	160°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ ON ₂ HCl	8.5	8.4	220°	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	8.3	8.1	
II. A = O(CH ₂ -CH ₂) ₂ N-.									
S. No.									
III. A = CH ₂ (CH ₂ -CH ₂) ₂ N-.									
1	189°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₂ HCl	9.3	9.4	5	212°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	7.8	8.0
2	207°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	8.1	8.3	6	248°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	7.7	8.0
3	178°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ ON ₂ Br ₂ HCl	7.5	7.7	7	(decomp.)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ HCl	7.5	7.7
4	196°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ HCl	8.9	9.0	8	272°	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ HClN ₂	7.9	8.1

*B and Br, serially same as in Table I

POTENTIAL LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART III

TABLE III

Hydrochlorides of α' -secondary amino-N-(α' -allyl(aryl benzyl) propionamides.

S.No.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
I. A = -NEt ₂ .								
1	172°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ ON ₃ .HCl	8.2	9.4	210°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₃ .HCl	8.5	9.0
2	180°	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	8.7	8.8	198°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl.HCl	8.2	8.4
3	160°	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Br.HCl	7.5	7.7	172°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br.HCl	7.5	7.4
4	165°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.7	8.9	109°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.8	8.5
5	190°	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.7	7.9	187°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	8.0	7.7
6	194°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.8	7.9	206°	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.4	7.6
7	179°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.8	7.6	197°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.4	7.3
8	240°	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ ON ₂ .HCl	8.3	8.1	245°	C ₂₀ H ₃₃ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	7.7	7.8
II. A = O(CH ₂ CH ₂) _n N-								
III. A = CH ₂ (CH ₂ -CH ₂) _n N-								
							Str. No.	
1	180°	C ₁₇ H ₂₉ ON ₂ .HCl	8.9	9.0	203°	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.8	7.7
2	192°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Cl.HCl	8.3	8.5	208°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.9	7.7
3	177°	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ ON ₂ Br.HCl	7.4	7.4	108°	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl ₂ .HCl	7.5	7.4
4	165°	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂ .HCl	8.3	8.3	215°	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ ON ₂ .HCl	8.0	7.8

N.B. R^o and R₁^o exactly same as in Table I

TABLE III

N-(α -Alkyl/aryl benzyl)- α' -halo-propionamides.

S. No.	M.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
			Found.	Reqd.
1	128°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ONCl	15.8	15.5
2	119°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ ONCl ₂	28.6	28.9
3	65°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ ONBrCl	4.6(N)	4.8(N)
4	130°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	14.7	14.5
5	126°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ ONCl ₃	38.2	38.0
6	Oil°	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ ONCl ₃	38.1	38.0
7	115°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ONCl ₃	36.3	36.2
8	106°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl	12.9	12.8

N.B. R* and R₁* are serially same as in Table I.

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